

Economic analysis of major vegetables marketing in Baraut block of Baghpat district of Uttar Pradesh

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Original Research Article Received on Feb 23, 2020 Revised on March 05, 2020 Accepted on March 23, 2020 Published on April 16, 2020</p> <p>Article Authors Lalit Kumar Verma, Shashank Tomer, Joginder Singh, Nitin Kumar Nag</p> <p>Corresponding Author Email verma.lalitkumar49@gmail.com</p>	<p>India is second largest producer of fruits and vegetables in world. India produces about 14% of world's vegetables from 15% world's area. The vegetable productivity in India is less than the world average productivity. Nearly 30-40% vegetables were wastage during the supply chain <i>i.e.</i> reaching from producer to consumer. Most of the marketing of vegetables in India is done in unorganized sector and very little quantity is marketed through organized sector. Present study was an attempt to study the marketing channels and to examine the marketing efficiency of organized retail chain. The Baraut blocks of Baghpat district was selected purposively for the present study. A total of 45 farmers, 4 intermediaries, 01 retailer and 60 consumers were selected. Vegetables <i>viz</i> tomato, cabbage, pea, okra and brinjal were selected for the study. Among the organized supply chain <i>i.e.</i> channel II, the cost incurred per kg of vegetables was much lower than the cost incurred in the traditional supply chain <i>i.e.</i> channel-I. In channel-I, the net return and marketing efficiency was higher for channel II than channel I for all the vegetables under study. At the same time organized supply chain was found to be smallest price spread. Hence organized supply chain (channel-I) was found more efficient as compared to unorganized supply chain (Channel-II). Hence it is advisable to the farmers to sell their produce through modern supply chain <i>i.e.</i> channel II as it is more efficient because the commodity was purchased directly from the producer.</p>
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In India total area under horticultural crops was 25.87 million hectare and production was 311.7 million tons in the year 2017-18. Fruits and vegetables together contribute about 92% of the total horticultural production in the country. India is the second largest producer of fruits and vegetables next to China in the world. It is grown in an area 9.575 million hectare with the productivity of 17.7 mt/ha which contributes 14% of the total world production of vegetables. In India, West Bengal, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha, Gujarat and Karnataka are the major vegetables growing states. Out of total vegetable production in India, Potato (28.9%), tomato (11.3%), onion

(10.3%) and Brinjal (8.1%) are the four major vegetables growing in the country which contributes about 58.6% of total vegetable production. Other important vegetables are cabbage (5.4%), cauliflower (4.6%), okra (3.9%) and peas (2.4%). The vast production base offers India tremendous opportunities for export. During 2017-18, India exported fruits and vegetables worth Rs. 9,410.81 crores/ 1,459.93 US\$ Millions which comprised of fruits worth Rs. 4,229.03 crores/ 655.90 US\$ Millions and vegetables worth Rs. 5181.78 crores/ 804.03 US\$ Millions. Major importers of Indian vegetables are UAE, Nepal, Sri Lanka, UK and Saudi Arabia accounting for about 55% of the total

vegetable exports from India. Keeping in view the increased production of vegetables and its export potential it is essential to work out the marketing channels followed by organized retail and its efficiency.

Present study was an attempt to study the marketing channels and to examine the marketing efficiency of organized retail chain.

Methodology

Sampling Procedure

The multistage purposive random sampling was used for selection of sample. The Baraut blocks of Baghpat district was selected purposively for the present study because farmers of in this districts were allocating larger area under vegetable cultivation. A list of all assigned retail outlets was prepared and Retailer retail outlet Baraut blocks was selected purposively for study. The primary data were collected from the selected farmers, wholesalers, retailer and consumers with the help of schedule and personal interview method. The 45 farmers, 04 intermediaries, 01 retailer and 60 consumers were selected for the study.

Analytical Tools

To work out the marketing efficiency of vegetables, Shepherd method was used. The marketing cost was estimated by using following formula:

$$C = C_1 + C_{m1} + C^{m2} + C_{m3} + \dots + C_{mi}$$

Where,

- C, is the total cost of marketing of the commodity
- C_f, is the cost paid by the producer from the time the produce leaves the farm till sells
- C_{mi}, is cost incurred by the ith middleman in the process of buying and selling of the product.

Marketing Margins

Following methods were used to find out the marketing margins (Srivastava *et al.*, 2010). The algebraic form of the equations presented below:

Absolute margin

$$A_{mi} = P_{Ri} - (P_{Pi} + C_{mi}) A$$

Percentage margins

It is the share of absolute margin in selling price.

$$P_{in} = \frac{[P_R - (P_p + C_{in})]}{P_R} \times 100$$

Mark-up

$$M_i = \frac{[P_R - (P_p + C_{in})]}{P_p} \times 100$$

Where,

- A_{mi} = Absolute margins of ith functionary
- P_{mi} = Percentage margin of ith functionary
- M_i = Mark-up of ith functionary
- P_{Ri} = Total value of receipts per unit (sale price)
- P_{Pi} = Purchase value of goods per unit (purchase price)
- C_{mi} = Cost incurred on marketing per unit

Price Spread

$$P_s = \left(\frac{\text{Absolute margin}}{\text{Consumers price}} \right) \times 100$$

Where,

P_s = Producer's /intermediaries' share in consumer's rupee.

Marketing Efficiency

Marketing efficiency was calculated using Shepherd's approach:

$$M. E. = C_p / (P_c + C + A_{mi})$$

Where,

- M.E. = Market efficiency
- C_p = Consumer's purchase price
- P_c = Marketing cost of producer
- C = Marketing cost of all the intermediaries involved in the channel
- A_{mi} = Marketing margin of the intermediaries involved in the channel.

Results and Discussion

Marketing Channels

Two marketing channels were prevailing in the study area. These are [1] Channel – I: Producer-Commission Agent/Adhatia – Retailer- Consumer and [2] Channel – II: Producer-Retailer – I was

prevailing in unorganized marketing chain whereas channel – II was found in organized sector.

Marketing Cost and Margin of Major Vegetables

The marketing cost, marketing margin and marketing efficiency for channel- I and channel- II for all the vegetable crops under study was presented in table 1. It is observed from the table 1 that the per quintal total marketing cost for the brinjal, cabbage, okra, pea and tomato was ranging between Rs. 227 to Rs. 327 in channel-I (unorganized sector), whereas it was Rs. 100 for all the vegetable crops in channel-II (organized sector). The market margin for all the vegetable crops was found to be Rs. 225 per quintal in channel-I and Rs. 190 per quintal in case of channel II. The contribution of producer's share in consumers' price was found to be higher in case of channel-II as compared to channel-I. In case of brinjal, cabbage, okra, pea and tomato, the producers' share in consumer's price was 55.05, 55.90, 70.15, 85.85 and 68.88% respectively under channel-I. In case of channel-II, the producer's share in consumers' price was 58.77, 62.07, 81.76, 92.45 and 73.39% for

brinjal, cabbage, okra, pea and tomato respectively (table 1).

Marketing Efficiency

The marketing efficiency is directly related to the cost involved to move the goods from producer to consumer and the quantum of service provided or desired by the consumer. If the cost paid by the consumer is less than the services provided to them then the channel will be called as efficient otherwise inefficient. More the number of intermediaries between the farmer and the consumer, the channel will be less efficient. It may be observed from the table 1 that the marketing efficiency for channel I for brinjal, cabbage, okra, pea and tomato was 2.22, 2.22, 3.34, 7.06 and 2.04% respectively and marketing efficiency for channel II for the same sequence of vegetables was 2.48, 2.63, 5.48, 13.24 and 3.75% respectively. The marketing efficiency was higher for channel II. Channel I has lower marketing efficiency since intermediaries are involved, resulting in higher marketing cost and marketing margin.

Table 1. Marketing cost, Marketing margin and Marketing efficiency in different channels for vegetables in Baghpat district

Particulars	Unit	Brinjal	Cabbage	Okra	Pea	Tomato
Channel - I						
Retailer's sale price/consumers purchase price	Rs. /Qt	1030	1050	1849	3902	1131
Total marketing cost	Rs. /Qt	327	327	327	327	227
Net marketing margin	Rs. /Qt	225	225	225	225	225
Net price received by farmers	Rs. /Qt	567	587	1297	3350	779
Price spread		21.84	21.42	12.16	5.76	19.89
Marketing efficiency		2.22	2.22	3.34	7.06	2.04
Channel - II						
Retailer's sale price/consumers purchase price	Rs. /Qt	1064	1036	1590	3840	1090
Total marketing cost	Rs. /Qt	100	100	100	100	100
Net marketing margin	Rs. /Qt	190	190	190	190	190
Net price received by farmers	Rs. /Qt	636	643	1300	3550	800
Price spread		17.85	18.33	11.94	4.94	17.43
Marketing efficiency		2.48	2.63	5.48	13.24	3.75

Conclusion

It is clear from above discussion that as the number of middlemen in marketing channel increases, the marketing efficiency of the channel decreases due to increase in marketing cost and margin. The total marketing cost and marketing

margin involved in unorganized channel was much higher than the organized channel for the vegetable crops under study. Since the marketing cost and marketing margin in former was higher, the marketing efficiency was low and for later, because of saving of marketing cost due to absence of market intermediaries and relatively low consumer's

price, the marketing efficiency was higher. The marketing efficiency for channel-I for brinjal, cabbage, okra, pea and tomato was 2.22, 2.22, 3.34, 7.06 and 2.04% respectively and marketing efficiency for channel-II for the same sequence of vegetables was 2.48, 2.63, 5.48, 13.24 and 3.75% respectively.

The study revealed that among different factors influencing the farmers to sell their vegetables to particular format in the supply chain was due to the spot payment, correct weight, proximity and remunerative price which were found to be major factors. However if it is seen, the farmers sell their vegetables to the unorganized marketing chain was mainly because of spot payment, correct weight, remunerative price and proximity of buyers.

References

- Ashturker, B. M., and C. D. Deole, (1985) Producers' Share in Consumers Rupee: A Case Study of Fruit marketing in Marathwada, *Indian J. Agric. Econ.*, **40**: 3.
- Chauhan, R. N., Singh, J. M. and Thakur, D. R. (1999) Marketing of vegetables in Uttar Pradesh, *Indian J. Agric. Mktg.*, **13**(2): 56.
- Horticulture Statistics at a Glance (2017) Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare, India.
- Kaul, G. L., (1997) Horticulture in India: Production, marketing and processing, *Indian J. Agric. Econ.*, **52**: 3.
- Kumar, M. P., (2012) A study on problems of marketing vegetables in farmers market, *Int. J. Rural Dev. Manag. Stud.*, **6**(1): 241-251.
- Reardon, T., P., Timmer and J., Berdegue, (2003) The rise of supermarkets in Africa, Asia and Latin America, *American J. of Agri. Economics*, **85**(5): 114-1146.
- Saikia, T. N. (1985) Price Structure of Pineapple: A Study in Meghalaya, *Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, **40**(3): 119-123.
- Singh, M., (1985) Price spread of vegetables marketing, *Indian J. Agric. Econ.*, **40**: 3.
- Singh, R. P. and Toppo, A. (2010) Economics of production and marketing of tomato in Kanke block of Ranchi district, *Indian J. of Agric. Marketing*, **24**(2):1-16.
- Singh, Ram and K. S., Suhag (2010) Role of state agricultural marketing board in marketing development in Haryana, *Indian J. of Agric. Marketing*, **24**(1): 38-48.
- State of Indian Agriculture (2017-18) Govt of India.
- Vegetable Statistics (2017) Indian Institute of Vegetable Research, Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India.